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SOCIAL ISSUES AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING THE EMPLOYMENT OF NEW SPECIALISTS

Annotation

In this article, in a market economy, the development of democratic values, the formation of civil society, human activity as an active subject of economic and political life, which, in turn, is necessary for the younger generation with the opportunity to learn and receive education throughout life, continuous education, creativity, the issues of creating the necessary conditions for the formation of a socially active and spiritually rich personality are explained.

Key words: Employment, living standards, incomes, wage, social policy, social progress, unemployment, labour market, kinds and types of the employment.

ЯНГИ МУТАХАССИСЛАР БАНДЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ МАСАЛАЛАРИ ВА ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ

Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада бозор иқтисодиёти шароитида демократик кадрятларни ривожлантириш, фуқаролик жамиятини шакллантириш йўлида инсон иқтисодий ва сиёсий ҳаётнинг фаол субъекти сифатида фаолият кўрсатиши, бу эса, ўз навбатида, ёш авлодни бутун ҳаёти давомида ўрганиш ва таълим олиш қobiliяти билан қуроллантириш зарурлигини, узлуксиз таълим ижодий, ижтимоий фаол ҳамда маънавий бой шахсни шакллантириш учун зарур шарт-шароитларни яратиш масалалари ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Олий таълим муассасаси, модернизациялаш, юқори малакали кадрлар, рейтинг, рақобатбардошлик, таълим сифати, ўқиш муддати, педагог ходим, битирувчи, ўзлаштириш кўрсаткичи, иш берувчи.

СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЗАНЯТОСТИ НОВЫХ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ

Аннотация

В данной статье в условиях рыночной экономики, развития демократических ценностей, формирования гражданского общества человек должен выступать активным субъектом экономической и политической жизни, что, в свою очередь, должно вооружить молодое поколение способность учиться и получать образование на протяжении всей жизни, непрерывное образование носит творческий, социально активный характер, освещаются вопросы создания необходимых условий для формирования духовно богатой личности.

Ключевые слова: Вуз, модернизация, высококвалифицированные кадры, рейтинг, конкурентоспособность, качество образования, срок обучения, профессорско-преподавательский состав, выпускник, степень овладения, работодатель.

Introduction. Today, the new Uzbekistan takes its place in the ranks of the world community. Every industry in the country is developing in a timely and correct manner, and every industry breathes renewal.

In a market economy, a person acts as an active subject of economic and political life in order to develop democratic values and form a civil society. This, in turn, indicates the need to equip the younger generation with the ability to learn and be educated throughout life. Continuous education creates the necessary conditions for the formation of a creative, socially active and spiritually rich personality.

“Today, the competitiveness of any country in the world market depends not only on the availability of natural resources, but also, first of all, on the regular training of a highly educated and disciplined workforce capable of mastering modern, regularly updated technologies. Without such a labor force, it is impossible to organize new industries that form a modern structure of the economy based on high technologies”[2].

The employment as a socio-economic phenomenon can be defined as socially useful activity of citizens connected with satisfaction of personal and societal needs and generating labor income (earnings). The employment is an essential characteristic of the economy and welfare of the population of

country, while representing the economic category and social problem.

Active employment of citizens is one of the most important factors for the effective functioning of the labor market. After all, the economic development of society is determined by the full realization of the rights of citizens to work[3].

As outlined in the UN Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, higher education is becoming the leading driver of sustainable economic growth in the world. Thanks to this, in the coming years, the world will maintain the pace of training highly qualified personnel, and by 2030 the predicted number of students in higher educational institutions will reach 414 million people, which is 4.2 times more than in 2000 [4]. Therefore, the issue of improving the quality of higher education is a necessary problem that needs to be addressed comprehensively, from the point of view of the fact that the foundation of knowledge acquired by modern specialists throughout their lives is created in higher educational institutions.

As an economic category the employment is a set of relations on the labour market regarding the participation of the population in the employment; expresses the extent of its inclusion in the labor, the degree of satisfaction of public needs and the needs of employees in paid jobs, in incomes.

The employment by the socially useful activities covers a wide range the working-age population. By the nature (sphere) of the activity of all employees can be divided into four large groups: 1) employed in remunerated activity; 2) soldiers engaged in activity that do not bring direct monetary gains (as the transition to the contract form of military service troops will be closer in status to employed in the economy); 3) students with job; 4) busy raising children and maintaining the household [3].

By way of participation in the labour force employed in the economy can be divided into three subgroups: 1) employees employed on the basis of sales of their workers; 2) employers/entrepreneurs, who are implementing their organizational and entrepreneurial skills; 3) self-employed (those who working for the wash account; members of production cooperatives that do not use hired labor on a regular basis) [4].

In accordance with the International classification of status in employment there are six occupational groups: 1) employees; 2) employers; 3) persons working for own account; 4) members of producers' cooperatives; 5) contributing family workers; 6) workers not classifiable by status [5].

Material and methods. Depending on the purpose of analysis uses a different classification of the employment. As a social problem, the employment plays a crucial role in the formation and development of professional abilities of each person in the formation and disclosure of his personality. The work in process of the employment creates the main wealth of the society and ensure its progressive development, contributes to social progress of the world community. In contrast of the employment – the unemployment has a negative impact on the life of a man, his family; is a destabilizing factor leading to stagnation, degradation of certain regions, social upheavals in society. Precisely because unemployment is a serious socio-political problem, the employment must be in the spotlight of society and the state, its socio-economic policy.

In this capacity, the state employment policy is a set of measures aimed at stimulating the involvement and effective use of citizens in the sphere of labour to achieve the goals of the individual and society. The basis for the creation and implementation of this policy is the concept of the employment as a system of beliefs, ideas, revealing the nature of employment of the population at a certain stage of socio-economic development of society. In Uzbekistan the concept of the employment is being worked out in conditions of formation of market economy with social orientation. Its main provisions are set out in the Law "On employment of population in the Republic of Uzbekistan". In this law also in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan reflects the basic principles of the employment [1].

The first principle reflects the exceptional right of citizens to freely use their abilities for productive and creative labour; forced labour in any form is not allowed (except for special cases established by law). Thus, the voluntary labour as the universal value enshrined in the law. The employment in sectors of the economy (national economy) is not the only sphere of public benefit activity. The sphere of work is one of equal and equally accessible spheres of activity, along with study, housework, parenting, social, religious and other activity. The citizens' unemployment is not a ground for bringing to administrative responsibility. People can freely choose the kind of activity, place and form of his abilities. This principle implies the right of man to work there and so where and how much it needed him. Regardless of gender, age, nationality, all are available in permanent, partial, temporary, occasional employment, part-time, flexible-time

arrangements. The role of society and the state with realization by the person of this principle is to create for everyone equal legal conditions of the employment.

The second principle reflects the responsibility of the state to create conditions for the realization of the rights of citizens to work and freely chosen the employment. The responsibility of the state associated with the principle of promoting employment of citizens, the disclosure of their interests and abilities when selecting the type and activity of public activity. The state employment promotion and creation conditions for it consists in the adjustment of indirect measures (economic, legislative, social) of the economic behavior of citizens in purchasing or relevant qualification for the employment or another activity, in finding a suitable job or school. The principle of the employment promotion has several aspects, along with indirect control of the desired direction of the employment; it is in active and interested participation of subjects in the social-labor relations (government, employers, trade unions) in directing the development of the employment and its regulation. Their close interaction in the development of the employment has a great impact on the qualitative characteristics of educational and vocational-qualification structure of the employed population and its industrial and demographic structure, socio-economic mobility and competitiveness.

The third principle reflects a comprehensive approach to solving employment problems; it involves the coordination of efforts of authorities of all levels, the interaction of mechanisms of state regulation and market self-regulation, the using of financial possibilities of extra-budgetary funds, funds of enterprises, public associations and citizens, to achieve economic and social efficiency of the programmes of the employment assistance.

Results. In a market economy there is no direct centralized administration and control system employment. In this system, the main regulators are the laws, decrees, legal acts, programmes to promote and encourage employment agreement between subjects of the social and labour relations at the national, regional, sectoral level and at the enterprise level; the important role belongs to investment, tax and financial-credit policy. The state in this system is the focal point, the creator of framework conditions for the functioning of the mentioned units controllers) of the system.

The state, through the employment policy at the state and regional levels, pursuing strategic and tactical objectives. The strategic employment policy objectives consist in achieving a high standard of living of the population, creation of conditions for versatile development of a person on the basis of improving the efficiency of the economy. Tactical goals aim to balance the supply and demand of labour on the basis of supply and demand of jobs, the provision of full, productive and effective employment. The market mechanism in the regulation of the employment aimed at increasing production efficiency and, consequently, the elimination of inefficient jobs, the release of workers not satisfying the requirements of demand. The state level of the state employment policy includes a range of active and passive measures to create and preserve jobs and prevent mass unemployment, keeping it on a socially acceptable level ("normal", "natural"), training and retraining the labour force that meets the requirements of scientific and technical progress and the labour market, the development and implementation of large programs and projects provide a way out of stagnation of the depressed regions, etc.

Discussion. Regional level of the public employment policy pursues the same strategic and tactical objectives as the state level, but involves better use of existing capacity in the region, innovative ways of solving the employment problems.

Among them are the elimination of administrative restrictions on labour mobility; training and retraining of the workforce with consideration of the peculiarities of labour in the region; support (administrative, fiscal) activity of employers to create jobs, including for people with limited employment opportunities; expansion of the range of public works for long-term residing in the status of unemployment; the establishment of cooperation between the administrations of labor-surplus and-deficient regions on the temporary use of labour-based contracts; the attraction of foreign capital in regions with a high unemployment rate, including for small and medium businesses and training the workforce.

The main direction of the state policy of the employment at all levels of regulation is to create economically viable jobs, which determine the demand for labour and ensure a balance with labor supply. The supply of labor greatly exceeded the demand, the state should conduct targeted preventive policy on social support for different vulnerable layers of the working - age population-could leave the labour market, reducing pressure on existing vacancies and reducing, thereby, the intensity of the current labour market.

An important factor in the improvement of social labor is the increase in the efficiency of the economy through the strengthening of labor motivation, through the transfer of the means of production in private hands (privatization), through the wage growth, through the provision of normal conditions of work and life, improving the competitiveness of workers, ensuring their social protection in case of dismissal, through the freedom of movement (migration) within the country and the region, through the creation of the housing market.

Conclusion. The account of the population by employment status allows to distinguish the following types of the employment [7]:

1) the productive employment is in the public spheres of material production; it brings the workers labor income; excludes hidden unemployment of persons formally employed, but do not produce anything (such persons form the production of excessive number of employees holding formal jobs non-economic and fall under the procedure of release in connection with the reduction or restructuring of production);

2) the useful employment, which applies to all socially important types of employment, including full-time study, military service, raising children, maintaining the home and personal farms, care for sick family members, elderly citizens, social and religious activities of able-bodied citizens;

3) the rational employment, which reflects the ratio of the productive employment to other forms of useful

employment or the distribution of labor resources of the society in the spheres of public benefit activities, including the distribution of labor potential of the occupations, industries, economy sectors;

4) the full-time employment in which all who wish to work at the prevailing (dominant) level of real wages have jobs; according to another estimate, the full-time employment occurs when the demand everyone to jobs comes from the economic feasibility of the proposed jobs. In relation to individual the full-time employment is work within normal working hours (week) established by law.

Thus, if the demand for economically viable jobs will be met by appropriate vocational qualification structure of the labour supply, this would mean the full-time employment. Without the continuous improvement of working places, creation of new, meeting modern requirements, and output from the production process of old, do not meet the economic feasibility of the impossible to achieve social progress, the interests of the society and of each person. The attainment of full employment cannot be achieved using a single market mechanism, need constant regulation of this process by the state and society, primarily in education, science, health, environmental, and national security, the functioning of the so-called natural monopolies (railroads, power and pipeline networks);

5) the effective employment is the employment that provides a decent income, growth of educational and professional level of working citizens on the basis of the growth of social productivity, and preserving the health of employees. By another measure, effective employment is a viable, productive, socially useful and rational employment, satisfying the social and personal needs. Thus crucial importance for any society is productive employment, which, first, determines the economic potential of the country; secondly, shape the level and quality of life of the population; third, is an essential component of the full-time and the effective employment of the key tasks of socio-economic policy.

The full-time employment is possible at a certain deviation of existing jobs from the status of economically feasible, the disparity between their occupational composition and educational level. In this situation, both the workers, and the state will bear the economic and social losses. Some workers will receive low wages, not providing normal existence, and the state society should receive less money in the budget and social funds.

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